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Holographic Recommendations in Brick-and-Mortar Stores

Completed Research

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Abstract

To keep up with their competition from e-commerce, traditional retailers are transitioning into an omnichannel retail that places the customer's shopping journey at the center of the business model by creating digital services that enhance the customer experience. A key service is in-store digital assistance. However, due to the scarcity of the required input data and the lack of a system design that would mitigate this problem; another remaining problem is the need for an output channel to present the personalized content that a customer would be willing to use. Following a design science approach, we identified requirements to reach the desire-end artifact and bridge them. Therefore, we propose an in-store recommender system that leverages mixed-reality technology to both gather necessary data and present relevant content in an immersive way, boosting the customer experience in brick-and-mortar stores.

Keywords

Recommender system, mixed reality, retail technologies, design science, information technology.

Introduction

Brick-and-mortar stores are closing down rapidly. Researchers have described the situation as the “retail apocalypse” (Berman 2018) and have argued that physical retail fails to provide a personalized shopping journey, which the contemporary customer expects (Carroll and Guzman 2013; Klaus 2013; Lazaris 2015). To mitigate the situation, physical stores have started adopting the concept of omnichannel retail (von Briel 2018; Piotrowicz and Cuthbertson 2014) where customer experience is at the center of the business model, and digital technologies are deployed to enhance that experience (Parise et al. 2016; Rigby 2011). In (Parise et al. 2016), the authors acknowledge the problem of meeting customers' expectations in brick-and-mortar and evaluate how digital technologies can aid the improvement of customer experience and of the transition to omnichannel retail. The authors consider the in-store touchpoint as essential and identify digital assistants, that allow customers to, e.g., perform product comparison, receive tailored offers or product recommendations, as one of the important models that can provide a more personalized and immersive experience. This is consistent with the study by (von Briel 2018) which points out key technologies such as Mixed Reality (MR), artificial intelligence, and real-time big data analysis as the trends that can provide a holistic experience to customers in omnichannel retail. The current limitations of physical stores, along with the desired features of a personalized in-store digital assistant, define the **problem space** we tackle. The **research gap** lies in the lack of literature on concrete use cases of mixed reality integrated with recommender systems in omnichannel retail environments. Specifically, no such in-store recommender system has been devised yet.

To this end, we propose an in-store assistant application that leverages head-mounted mixed reality devices, demonstrated by us using the Microsoft HoloLens as an example, to deploy a recommender system (RS). Such devices enrich the physical world around their user by a seamless integration of digital objects

(Milgram and Kishimo 1994), are thus user-centered and immersive by design, and therefore the ideal technology to address our research gap. We leverage the potential of the HoloLens both as an output channel to display recommendations and, by means of the different input channels provided by the device, as a source of valuable information about the customers’ behavior in the stores. We follow the design science methodology (Hevner et al. 2004) to analyze the problem space, extract requirements for the desired artifact, and match these requirements to design an instantiation prototype.

In the following, we discuss relevant previous work and the necessary theoretical and technological background as well as our methodological approach. Following the latter, we conceptualize our in-store MR recommender system and discuss its benefits and limitations as well as avenues of future research.

Previous Work

To elaborate on the problem space and derive requirements for an in-store recommender system based on mixed reality, two branches of research bear relevance – previous attempts to deploy recommender systems in physical retail with their advantages and shortcomings, and related use cases of mixed reality in store.

Mixed Reality and its Applications in Retail

Mixed reality devices (Ohta and Tamura 2014) such as the HoloLens display holograms: three-dimensional, digital objects rendered on the display in front of the user’s eyes to create the impression that they are part of the real world. The HoloLens enriches holograms with light and sound effects to further increase realism. In particular, emulation of spatial sound effects is possible via the integrated speakers. A multitude of sensors (Table 1, left column) enables not only the display of holograms but also to interact with them. Connectivity is another strong point of the device as it supports the two major wireless technologies—Wi-Fi and Bluetooth, that allow to connect to other devices, local networks, or the internet.

Sensors	Raw Input data	Output channels
Inertial measurement unit (1x)	3D position	Holographic display
Front camera (1x)	Head orientation	Audio speakers
Depth camera (1x)	Images	
Environment camera (4x)	Speech	
Ambient light sensor (4x)		
Microphone (4x)		

Table 1. Input and Output Channels Provided by the Microsoft HoloLens

An overview over the current state of the art in MR for digital retail is given by the recent study of (Jain and Werth 2019). Contemporary literature on MR and its applications in retail suggests that it can improve customer experience in terms of both utilitarian and hedonic values (Papagiannidis et al. 2017). In (Meegahapola and Perera 2017), the authors proposed a smartphone-based MR system to enhance in-store shopping experience. Another use case has been demonstrated in (Spreer and Kallweit 2014), where MR has been deployed at the point of sales to evaluate acceptance of the technology. Recently, researchers from the RS domain have discovered the technology, too, yielding first initial concepts for combinations of MR and RS (Álvarez Márquez and Ziegler 2017a, 2017b; Pilloni et al. 2017). However, there is still a lack of a strategy and model to integrate RS and MR devices efficiently, actually exploiting all of the technological possibilities both as a source of input data and as an output channel for recommendations. With our system, we aim to assist customers by providing personalized assistance augmenting their physical reality with an immersive user interface (UI) based on virtual 3D objects to supersede non-immersive 2D displays (Papagiannidis et al. 2017)

Recommender Systems and their Application to Physical Retail

Recommender systems are a type of information filtering. They use machine learning to determine users’ preferences to generate a ranked list of items relevant for them, based on their past behavior and similarities to other customers. A common algorithm is collaborative filtering (CF) (Goldberg et al. 1992). CF is often based on matrix factorization using methods like singular value decomposition (SVD) (Billsus et al. 1998).

To improve the quality of recommendations, practitioners can also incorporate auxiliary information using algorithms such as SVDFeature (Chen and Lu 2012). Context-awareness, i.e., the use of “contextual signals to become more human-centered” (Fischer 2012) is another essential extension of RS.

Regarding in-store recommendations, smartphones are currently the most popular approach. Their main advantage is the offered access to relevant data inputs: Not only does the smartphone store a lot of personal information about its user, the sensors integrated in a modern smartphone also allow retailers to connect to the customer inside the store. For example, real-time position information can be obtained using Bluetooth beacons, leveraging the WiFi received signal strength (RSS), or the GPS. An early example was the smartphone-based store RS for shopping malls by Fang et al. (Fang et al. 2012) that implicitly captures a customer’s preferences for stores by tracking their positions using WiFi-RSS. Compared to a conventional RS that does not consider the customer’s context, the system resulted in higher satisfaction and recommendation accuracy. The system was perceived as more useful and easier to use. However, as recently identified by (Pimenidis et al. 2018), there are remaining challenges concerning mobile RS such as addressing the complexity of data and fully exploiting the potential for personalized advertisements.

Technologies other than smartphones have been used more scarcely. One option is to analyze the live video data from surveillance cameras to obtain behavioral data (Mora et al. 2019). A fundamental drawback in this scenario is the dependence on additional devices to output the generated recommendations. A second alternative, mostly limited to fashion stores, are smart mirrors, which use integrated cameras to analyze the visual appearance of customers or recognize radio-frequency identification (RFID) tags in nearby products to infer customers’ interests. As an example, this information can then be used to recommend clothing (Chao et al. 2009; Hanke et al. 2018). Besides the limited scope of the method – fashion and related domains – the lack of personalization and immobility of the mirrors are additional shortcomings. Regarding omnichannel retail approaches, the authors in (Carnein et al. 2019) developed a recommender architecture which can gather and integrate data from different online channels. However, the authors did not include physical store data, and therefore did not consider in-store requirements such as context awareness which is desired in an in-store application (Parise et al. 2016).

Research Methodology

We adopt the design science research (DSR) methodology which creates and evaluates IT artifacts that “solve identified organizational problems” (Hevner et al. 2004) and has been successfully applied to related scenarios in RS research (Zszech et al. 2019). The DSR framework involves six steps: 1) problem identification and motivation, 2) definition of the objectives for a solution, 3) design and development, 4) demonstration, 5) evaluation and 6) communication. In this paper, we focus on the first four. We start with a description of the problem space (step 1) which is manifested in the form of requirements (R) to propose a solution artifact that assists customers in stores (step 2). We identify suitable desired ends to create an in-store MR application to deploy a recommender system and fulfill the identified requirements (step 3). These finally allow us to design and demonstrate an instantiation of the proposed system. Thus, our result is an overview of functionalities and limitations of different systems, which can be used to establish an adequate processing pipeline for an in-store mixed reality RS. Even though the empirical evaluation and communication will be addressed in future research, we outline the plans to do so in the following section. Augmenting this methodology, (Avdiji and Winter 2019) defined nine different gaps that can be targeted in DSR. With our contribution, we specifically address the “Validity Gap” defined as the “mismatch between the desired ends of the DSR project and the design requirements of the design artifact”.

As our starting point, we conducted a literature review following (Webster and Watson 2002) using the online databases AIS eLibrary and Google Scholar. We defined a set of key concepts, to then identify relevant papers, giving an understanding of the domain problems, which is synthesized in the ‘Requirement Extraction’ section. In order to match these requirements, we design and develop a prototypical artifact based on Capelleveen et al.’s Recommender Canvas design methodology as guidance framework (Capelleveen et al. 2019) which outlines the decision-making process when designing an RS.

Requirement Extraction

In order to extract the requirements, a review of the problem space is required. As discussed in the introduction, the rapid development of digital technology is changing the business and brick-and-mortar

retailers must transform digitally (von Briel 2018; Parise et al. 2016; Piotrowicz and Cuthbertson 2014; Rigby 2011). The optimal approach to this depends on the retail sector, but there are general trends. At its core, retailers need to understand the customer and create digital services that enhance their experience to generate business value. One manifestation of this is a personalized digital assistant that boosts the customer journey (Parise et al. 2016) as it allows retailers to suggest tailored options that can positively stimulate the customer, leading to higher satisfaction and retention. Furthermore, it contributes to a successful conversion in the sales process.

Requirement		Description
R1	Data gathering	The system should be able to extract the potential inputs from the Microsoft HoloLens.
R2	Product recognition	The system is required to determine which product the consumer is interacting with.
R3	Personalized product recommendations	The system should be able to handle the different types of input from the HoloLens and create valuable recommendations out of it, based on the location of the customer.
R4	Personalized product comparison	The system requires selecting the products that are most relevant to the user based on the product with which he desires comparisons.
R5	Personalized offers	The system is required to determine which offers are near to user and select the ones more relevant for them.
R6	Representation	Creating an immersive UI, which display the personalized content and provide value to customers.

Table 2. Identified/Extracted Requirements for the Desired Artifact

In our scenario, we achieve personalization using implicit and explicit data about the user. The HoloLens (and similar MR devices) can provide the underlying information as input to the recommender system and overcome the common data acquisition bottleneck in RS, however the precise inputs first have to be identified and extracted (R1), as can be seen in Table 2.

Based on the initial inputs, the system then has to assess the customer's needs. In particular, the RS must be capable of detecting the products that the customer is exploring and interacting with (R2) to be able to display related content to assist the customer. From a technical point of view, retailers need to create a recognition and tracking. The product recognition has to be stable enough for the user to have a satisfactory shopping experience. If an object is identified and tracked, this triggers the display of relevant UI elements. In our prototype, we specifically integrated buttons to query offers, recommendations and product comparisons. In (Lazaris 2015), the author analyzes which online practices and technologies could be transferred to brick-and-mortar stores. A large number of study participants expressed interest in self-service functionalities, being offered special prices and coupons by alerts when inside the store, but also in in-store recommendations and location-based offers. This aligns with a recent study by (Betzing et al. 2019), where most participants expressed a positive likeliness to use in-store services like product recommendation, exploration and comparison. Therefore, HoloLens and retailer's data can be used to create digital services as to provide in-store assistance to customers.

The inputs from the MR device (R1), in particular the current object of interest (R2), promise the potential for precise recommendations. However, they must be processed and integrated into the design of the system, which yields the third requirement: the processing of the input data, which generates real-time contextual recommendations (R3). Besides the mere recommendation of relevant products, product comparison is another integral part of the shopping journey: It reduces information overload and facilitates the decision-making process (Huddleston et al. 2018). Therefore, the system should support personalized product comparisons (R4). With the user profile, and the retailer being able to infer a customer's taste, stores can then also present relevant discounts, offers or promotions based on the user's preferences and context. Consequently, the system should be able to provide location-based offers (R5).

Recommendations, offers or the ability to compare products can only be effective if they are presented to the user in the right way to provide hedonic and utilitarian value (R6). The UI of a system is the only part which the user sees and interacts with. The HoloLens with its holographic display poses a very powerful

output channel which however has its own specifics that have to be dealt with: For head-mounted MR devices, the UI has to be designed in the context of the three-dimensional surrounding world as opposed to just two dimensions for a typical UI. (Parise et al. 2016) argues that proper deployment of technologies can improve customer experience and hence, as the last requirements of the system, the system should present the produced output in a way that provides customers with a better shopping experience. It can be argued that by matching the mentioned system requirements in Table. 2., the aim of developing a shopping assistance to tackle the personalization aspect of the customers with immersive media can be accomplished.

An In-store Mixed Reality Recommender System

The proposed MR recommender system assists customers throughout their shopping journey and is developed as an application running on the Microsoft HoloLens device and other MR devices with similar capabilities. In our scenario, while the app is deployed by the retailer, the device is owned by the customer and thus has access to personal information which is needed to provide recommendations. The recommendations leverage the customer's behavior in store but also other information such as historical transactions associated to an app account. To match the requirements, we first assess which of the inputs provided by the device (Table. 1) can be used to extract valuable information about the user. Then, we conceptualize the recommender system to provide personalized content and display it via the HoloLens.

Input Data

The Microsoft HoloLens provides a set of inputs as shown in Figure. 1 (left) that can be channeled to become both explicit and implicit inputs to the recommender system. Multiple sensors such as the inertial measurement unit and depth sensor work together to determine important cues, e.g., the current position of the user with respect to the world around them and their head gaze, i.e. the rough gazing direction. This information can also be stored over time providing a full history of a customer's positions and orientations in the store. Head gaze and position information can be mapped to the physical environment to determine which areas or departments the user is focusing on. Using the integrated camera, we can even monitor the user's field of view to determine which precise product they are examining at each point in time. The involved object recognition can be realized using SDKs such as Vuforia (Microsoft 2019a) that allow the recognition of arbitrary objects based on sample photographs to display digital objects anchored around them (R2). Another use for the camera is hand gesture recognition. The HoloLens also provides a point and click interface that can be used to provide explicit inputs like personal information or preferences. With the integrated microphone, the system can take speech as an input, too. Apart from these input streams coming from the HoloLens itself, the system can incorporate information maintained in the retailer's IT systems like explicit product ratings by users or product information, addressing the requirement R1.

Recommender System Design

	Goal	Domain Characteristic	Functional Design	Technique Selection	Interface Design	Evaluation
R1	X	X				
R2	X					
R3	X		X	X		
R4	X		X	X		
R5	X		X	X		
R6	X				X	

Table 3. Requirements Matching Based on the Recommender Canvas

Designing a recommender system is a complex process, and engineers are faced with a growing number of design-related decisions. We resort to the Recommender Canvas design methodology as specified in the previous section. It categorizes the design process into six areas: goal, domain characteristics, functional design, technique selection, interface design and evaluation. Each area addresses some of the requirements identified in the preceding section as depicted in Table 3.

Figure 1. Overall System Design and Data Flow

Goal

The aim of the proposed system is to assist customers in brick-and-mortar stores by deriving relevant products for the user based on their inferred taste and contextual behavior. Taking advantage of a MR device such as the HoloLens, the final goal is an enjoyable immersive experience also reducing the information overload in decision making. The system helps to personalize the in-store shopping experience by offering personalized and contextual recommendations as shown in Fig. 2 and presenting them in an attractive manner. The system is to support retailers in creating an important point of interaction with the customer in stores, which is crucial in omnichannel retailing and valuable in physical retail.

Domain Characteristics

The design of the system is influenced by characteristics of retail as the target domain. One of the biggest challenges for the adaptation of recommender systems in offline retail is the availability of input data. By tapping the HoloLens inputs (Table. 1) as a source of additional data as outlined in the preceding subsection, we can overcome limitations of existing approaches such as the lack of real-time contextual information that ultimately helps retailers to understand personal preferences better and to eventually provide a purchase experience centered around the individual. The integration of these inputs and of auxiliary information, e.g. about the placement of products, can be achieved by data hybridization using SVDFeature (Chen et al. 2011; Chen and Lu 2012), addressing R1.

Functional Design Considerations

The functional design of the system is driven by the question of what functionalities a user might expect from the system. Contemporary customers have a desire to be treated by retailers on a personal level, as stated in R2, R3, and R4. The personalization is handled by the system's high level of context-awareness and the use of real-time information (Fischer 2012).

Technique Selection

We propose to follow a collaborative filtering approach using SVDFeature (Chen and Lu 2012) which is based on matrix factorization as discussed in the Previous Work section and provides a trade-off between complexity and flexibility. In particular, it allows to incorporate all of the inputs provided by the HoloLens. Another point of consideration is the training method to use. Here minimizing the loss function using stochastic gradient descent (Koren 2008) is a common approach that allows to incorporate information from new users in an organic way. Furthermore, the authors in (Schrage 2019) suggest that in-store recommendations are more relevant when customers are close to the suggested products and that location has the strongest impact on the effectiveness advertising and personalization. Consequently, we propose to use the location of the user in post-context filtering (Adomavicius et al. 2011), e.g., at the department level. In this matter, we obtain a list, which estimates the customers preferences for all the retail products and which is filtered based on the department, which can be ranked to offer the Top-N more relevant products to the customers, fulfilling (R3). Furthermore, to deploy a personalized product comparison, the system

leverages the same ranked list of recommendations and filters it based on the specific type of product the customer is interacting with and presents product comparisons with the Top-N products (R4). Similarly, for the personalized offers, the system leverage the filtered list from the department, and filter again based on the offers available to display the nearest Top-N offers which are predicted to be the more relevant to the customers (R5), reducing in a time-sensitive touchpoint the overload of information and creating a more satisfactory customer journey in a time-sensitive touch point which is physical retail. The Top-N number of product presentation will depend on the specific retail scenario. For our prototype, the Top-2 items are displayed in the recommendations and product comparison, while in the offers option the item which is estimated to be the most preferable for the customer is displayed, as shown in Figure 2.

Interface Design

Figure 2. Screenshot from the Functional Prototype of the Interface

The interface of the system provides easy navigation and intuitive visualizations as depicted by the screenshots from our prototype in Figure 2. The voice commands “start” and “stop” are used to enable / disable the UI. This UI anchors itself to the product focused by the user which is determined using image recognition. This allows to move freely while using the interface, making it more tangible. In Figure 2, top left, the product of interest is a box of milk. Holographic buttons realized using the Microsoft MRTK toolkit (Microsoft 2019b) can be focused using a cursor (Fig. 2, blue circle) and activated using either hand gestures, voice commands or the HoloLens clicker, to access all functionalities: recommendations, product comparison and special offers. These address requirements R3, R4 and R5, respectively. The “Offers” screen (Fig. 2, top right) shows current discounts applicable to nearby products and increases the chance of purchases. The “Recommendations” (Figure. 2, bottom left) show related products and can lead to cross-sells. Comparison of alternatives is possible, too, (Figure. 2, bottom right): Alternate options of the same product category are display to this end. At any point in time, the user can make a buying decision based on the additional information provided by the recommender using the “Buy” button.

Evaluation

To evaluate the system performance, an empirical evaluation is required to validate the claim that the system improves a customer’s shopping experience in practice. Specifically, we plan the deployment of our prototype in a retail-like lab environment and later also in a field test in an actual store. As the precise test scenario, we opt for supermarkets or grocery stores as they offer a large variety of products which also

frequently changes over time due to the introduction of new products. These characteristics, on one hand, increase the need for means of product comparison particularly often, and, on the other hand, also make RS particularly useful as customers often stick with the same product out of a certain product category and recommendations or special offers could help retailers to steer customers towards alternative or newly introduced products which, e.g., offer wider margins. Given the fact that the omnichannel approach to retail puts the customer at the center of the business model, we opt to follow a user-centric study approach such as recently demonstrated by (Pu and Chen 2011) and (Knijnenburg et al. 2012) to evaluate the acceptance and impact of the system on the target users. Standard quantitative measures such as precision and recall can be used to measure the quality of the recommendations. Beyond that, (Capelleveen et al. 2019) also consider ways to optimize the recommender system further. Given the prototypical nature of our system, optimization methods are not yet applicable in the scope of this article but will follow in subsequent steps. Additionally, there are many directions in which the system can be extended, for example by a specialization for a specific type of retail and conducting qualitative case studies towards deployment of the technology.

Discussion, Conclusion and Future Work

Providing a personalized experience to customers has traditionally paid off for retailers. Nowadays, with the advances in fields such as immersive technologies, data science and AI; brick-and-mortar stores have the opportunity to integrate innovative solutions, not by mimicking the e-commerce but by analyzing in-store customer desires and adapting technologies that have been proven to be key success factors in modern retail, like recommender systems (McKinsey & Company 2013), and technologies that have the potential to enrich customer experience like MR (Papagiannidis et al. 2017). We thus proposed to employ the Microsoft HoloLens as a valuable source of both input and output to deploy a tailored in-store recommender system. Our aim was to provide a clear framework which was organized according to the Recommender Canvas to help retail practitioners and researchers to adopt and use these technologies. Thereupon, the system aims to aid the transition of traditional retail into the omnichannel model.

In the proposed scenario, the HoloLens can continuously monitor what shelves or products a customer is examining, collecting more information and allowing retailers to assist users better. The increased collection of input data reduces the problem of data sparsity resulting in more accurate recommendations for the customer. An alternative approach to obtain similar real-time information is computer vision (Mora et al. 2019), which however has some limitations. For example, to infer which product a customer is seeing using standard surveillance cameras would require a large number of cameras placed in different locations, powerful hardware, and algorithms to analyze the video streams. In contrast, the HoloLens provides this information as a single integrated device which does not need any additional hardware or software to be set up. Furthermore, there are also evident advantages regarding the output. Perhaps the most important one is the immersive environment for the end-user. This interaction is similar to that with real objects, making it more natural than in mobile phones and fully immersive environments. This immersion makes the shopping experience more pleasant to the user and more streamlined towards a buying decision.

In its current form, our system has some remaining limitations that are mainly connected with the novelty of the proposed artifact. The first is the accessibility and usability of its hardware. Also, gesture-based interactions typically require some time for new users to get used to it. Regarding the hardware used, the next generation of the HoloLens has already been released. Some of its features are more precise position and eye gaze estimations which would improve the precision of the recommender system and reduce some of the current limitations. A challenge for retailers will be to understand the customers' perception regarding privacy. Customers usually express higher privacy concerns in personalized services than in non-personal ones (Wetzlinger et al. 2017). Through user studies, it will be interesting to see to which extent immersion can aid the perception of the personalized recommender system.

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